

INFLUENCE OF RELATIVE HUMIDITY ON FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION IN ARALL3™

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental study of humidity effect on crack propagation in ARALL3. A comparison between crack growth measured on the base aluminium alloy and on the ARALL3 for the same relative humidity, shows in both cases a similar enhancement of the crack growth rate with respect to reference data obtained at 0%RH. The increase of the delamination growth rate observed in ARALL3 under the action of humidity is directly related to the acceleration of the crack propagation in the metallic parts of the material.

Keywords : ARALL , environment , relative humidity , fatigue , crack propagation

1. INTRODUCTION

The structural weight of aircraft has a significant effect on flight performance, which leads to the development of new hybrid materials exhibiting high strength level and low density. One such material is the ARALL family which consists of a stacking sequence of thin aluminium sheets bonded together by an adhesive impregnated with unidirectional high modulus aramid fibers (1-3). Crack propagation in ARALL3 results from the combination of two simultaneous mechanisms: the growth of a crack in the aluminium sheets and the development of a delamination in the crack wake. The load is transferred from the cracked aluminium alloy to the intact fibers, thus highly reducing the stress intensity factor at the crack tip. These mechanisms confer outstanding fatigue crack growth properties and possibilities of crack self arrested (4-7). Due to the nature of ARALL3, the action of humidity on each component could modify the global fatigue crack behavior. The objective of this work is to evaluate the influence of relative humidity on the crack propagation behavior of ARALL3.

2. EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

The material used in this investigation is a 3/2 ARALL3 laminate in the 0,4% stretched condition. This material is composed of a stacking sequence of thin aluminium sheets (7475 T76) bonded together by an epoxy adhesive impregnated with unidirectional

high aramid fibers of respective thicknesses of 0.3 and 0.22mm. The mechanical properties of both the ARALL3 and the 7475 T76 are shown in table 1 (8).

E (MPa)		R _{0,2} (MPa)		R _m (MPa)		A (%)	
L	T	L	T	L	T	L	T
68000	51000	587	317	828	373	2,2	-
Mechanical properties of ARALL3							
69000		476		545		13	
Mechanical properties of 7475 T76							

TABLE 1

Tests were performed on CCT specimens 80mm wide and 240mm long, on an Instron servo-hydraulic machine. The applied fatigue loading was sinwave tensile stress with a constant amplitude ratio R of 0,1 and a test frequency of 20Hz. The crack length was measured with a 100 magnification stereo-microscope fixed on a travelling device of 0,01mm resolution. In order to run tests under a controlled environment, a cell was clipped onto the specimen allowing to operate in relative humidity air ranging from 0% to 85% at room temperature. Due to the production process of the environmental air, the drier air (0%RH) contains less than 500 ppm water vapor. Specimen orientation was chosen so as to have the loading axis parallel to the fibers. A four-step specific testing procedure was developed in order to produce the same crack path for all the experiments. After an initial propagation of 6mm on each side of the central notch, the loading amplitude was slowly increased by steps of 1,5% to 2,5% with a constant loading ratio of 0,1. Thus the propagation was performed at increasing load steps for crack growth rates ranging from 10^{-10} m/cycle up to 10^{-6} m/cycle. For the different humidity rates, the loading history (loading amplitude versus crack length) during this procedure was similar for all the tests. A specific optical technique was developed to performe in situ measurements of the dimension of the delamination area on the external aluminium sheet (photo 1). A crack profile in ARALL3 laminate is presented in figure1. For comparison purpose on the environmental influence, additional tests were performed on a monolithic aluminium alloy sheet of a 7475 T76 alloy of a thickness of 1,4mm on specimen having the same geometry as ARALL3 ones.

Photo 1: Delamination area ; $da/dN = 8,3 \times 10^{-7}$ m/cycle

Figure 1: Geometry of the fatigue crack in ARALL3

3. RESULTS

3.1 Reference tests on 7475T76

The crack growth rate (da/dN) of 7475 T76 versus the effective stress intensity factor (ΔK_{eff}) under air relative humidity rate of 0%, 20%, 60% and 85% at room temperature are shown in figure 2. In order to get a more precise view of the environmental effect, prior results obtained under vacuum have been plotted in the same figure (9). The analysis of the curves brings out the following observations. In the whole observed range, the crack growth rates in dry air are lower than in moist air and the crack growth behaviors for 60%RH and 85%RH moist air are similar. At 20%RH the observed behavior is medium between the dry air and the moist air environments. Apart from the near threshold zone, the ratio of the maximum crack growth rates in dry air against that at 85%RH is about three times at a ΔK_{eff} of $4\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, but the threshold stress intensity factor in vacuum is twice higher than for the other environments. At higher growth rates ($> 5 \times 10^{-7}\text{m/cycle}$) the curves in air and in vacuum meet as the environmental effect is assumed to vanish.

Figure 2: da/dN - ΔK_{eff} diagrams for 7475 T76 aluminium alloy

3.2 Crack propagation in ARALL3

The results of fatigue crack propagation in ARALL3 in air with relative humidity rates of 0%, 20%, 40%, 60% and 85% at room temperature are shown in figure3.

Figure 3: Fatigue crack growth of ARALL3 for different relative humidity

The analysis of the curves brings out the following observations. Near the threshold ($da/dN < 10^{-9}$ m/cycle) no substantial influence of air humidity on the crack propagation rate has been detected, but at crack growth rates higher than 10^{-9} m/cycle the crack growth rates in dry air are systematically lower than in moist air. In the medium range 10^{-9} m/cycle $< da/dN < 10^{-8}$ m/cycle, the fatigue crack propagation is slightly influenced by the environment. For both materials and for all environments, the ratio of the crack growth rate in moist air (x%RH) against the rate in dry air ($\chi = (da/dN)_{x\%RH} / (da/dN)_{0\%RH}$) was defined. The maximum crack growth ratio χ between dry air and 85%RH air is constant and in the order of 2. For $da/dN > 10^{-8}$ m/cycle, the crack growth rate in humid environments increase suddenly, the acceleration being more pronounced for the highest humidity rate. In this range, the ratio χ between dry air and 85%RH air reaches 4 which is the maximum of the humidity influence. At the highest growth rates, the influence of humidity decreases, this effect being more pronounced for the highest humidity. As in the aluminium alloy, the influence of humidity on the crack propagation behaviour in ARALL3 appears to be very similar at 60%RH and 85%RH, which suggests the existence of a saturation step in the influence of humidity on the fatigue crack growth mechanism.

3.3 Delamination growth rate in ARALL3

For all the tests, the geometry of the delamination area is a triangular shaped, the crack tip in the aluminium alloy corresponding to the top of the triangle (photo 1). The delamination growth rate of ARALL3 (db/dN) under relative humidity of 0%, 40% and 85% versus the load amplitude is represented in a double logarithmic diagram (figure4). The propagation of the delamination boundary can be described with a PARIS'law for all the tests. For a giving load amplitude, the delamination growth rate is related to humidity, while the slopes of the curves are apparently not influenced by humidity. In the whole studied range, the ratio is 3,4.

Figure 4: Delamination growth of ARALL3 for different humidity rate

3.4 Fractography study

Photo 2 and 3 give an illustration of the fracture surface morphology at $da/dN = 5.10^{-7}$ m/cycle on the based aluminium and on the aluminium layer of the ARALL3 at 85%RH. In both cases, the fracture surface represents a transgranular cracking with striation formation. These fractographic observations clearly show that the same propagation mechanisms is operative in both cases.

Photo 2: Fracture surface morphology of 7475 T76 aluminium alloy for 85%RH
 $da/dN = 5 \times 10^{-7}$ m/cycle

Photo 3: Fracture surface morphology of ARALL3 for 85%RH
 $da/dN = 3,82 \times 10^{-7}$ m/cycle

4. DISCUSSION

The influence of the relative humidity on the delamination growth rate in ARALL3 and on the crack propagation rate in the aluminium alloy sheets can be related as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Comparison of delamination crack growth ratio for different relative humidity

Two salient features emerge from this figure: firstly, the evolution of the delamination growth rate is similar for all the environments, and secondly, in the explored rate range, da/dN and db/dN are quite equal. This observation suggests that for $5 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{m/cycle} < db/dN < 10^{-6} \text{m/cycle}$, there is no direct action of water vapor on the delamination mechanism kinetics. The delamination growth rate interval considered here is very much higher than the diffusion coefficient of the water vapor in the ARALL measured by VERBRUGGEN (10), thus the humidity cannot influence the delamination process. This analysis can be connected to a study realized by ROEBROEKS (4) who shows that the delamination shape is related to the state of the aramid fibers located in the crack wake, and according to the author a triangular shape corresponds to a configuration where there are only unbroken fibers in the crack wake. In all the tests performed in the present study the delamination shape was triangular, which suggests that there is no degradation of the mechanical properties of the fibers due to moist air.

So, in a first approximation, the delamination growth rate could be considered equal to the crack growth rate for every environmental conditions and for the experimental conditions herein considered. Consequently, the influence of humidity on crack propagation in ARALL3 might be controlled by the humidity effect on the fatigue crack propagation of the base aluminium alloy. The influence of environment on fatigue behavior of aluminium alloys can be broken down into two different stages (11,12). At crack rates higher than 10^{-8}m/cycle the environmental effect due to ambient air has been related to the adsorption of water vapor on freshly created surfaces, and near the threshold ($da/dN < 10^{-9} \text{m/cycle}$) hydrogen is produced by the dissociation of adsorbed water vapor molecules, and thus dragged by dislocation come and fro movement inducing an hydrogen assisted crack growth mechanism. Comparison of growth rates of 7475 T76 in dry air with previous intrinsic data obtained in vacuum shows similar data in the interval $10^{-8} \text{m/cycle} < da/dN < 10^{-6} \text{m/cycle}$.

Tests perform in vacuum on ARALL3 are not yet available. So comparison of the behavior of ARALL3 and 7475T76 can only be made in the range $10^{-8} \text{m/cycle} < da/dN < 10^{-6} \text{m/cycle}$ where crack propagation could be considered an intrinsic one. χ variations with respect to the reference rate at 0%RH are presented in figure6.

Figure 6: Comparison of humidity effect on 7475 T76 alloy and ARALL3

A progressive decrease of the humidity influence is observed when the crack growth rate increases on both materials. But for 60% and 85%RH a substantial influence of humidity is still observed in ARALL3 at higher growth rates, while no influence is observed in the aluminium alloy. Observation made on the fracture surfaces of the two materials (photo 2 and 3) tested in the same environmental conditions shows identical morphologies supporting similar propagation mechanisms. This difference in the sensitivity of ARALL3 to humidity as compared to the 7476 T76 alloy could be explained by some change in the crack closure in relation with very different crack wake. It can be noticed that the above comparison has been made using effective data in the 7475 T76 alloy and nominal data in ARALL3. Crack closure measurements in ARALL3 would give useful informations.

5. CONCLUSION

From an experimental study of the influence of humidity in ambient air on fatigue crack propagation in ARALL3 under constant amplitude loading, the following conclusions can be drawn out :

- Relative humidity enhances crack growth rates in a similar way in ARALL3 and in 7475T76 aluminium alloy .
- Acceleration of growth rate is observed for relative humidity ranking from 0% to 60%. The controlling process seems to be saturated for relative humidity higher than 60%.
- The enhancement of delamination growth rate with relative humidity rate in ARALL3 is directly related to the acceleration of crack propagation induced by humidity in the metallic parts of the material.

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